

Impact of Digitalisation on Women Empowerment in India

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Abstract—Digitalisation Has not only opened up new opportunities for Economic growth and social development but has also posed Problems and challenges. Digitalisation enhance wide range Of developmental applications in agriculture, industry and social Sectors Information Technology Provides unique opportunities for human development. and it has been widening the gaps between and within Countries, regions, gender while increasing disparities divide Between the rural-urban, rich-poor, elite also Within the different categories of women in various spheres of Activity. ICT playing very important role to build up women capacities and it involves in productive activities and family and Social transformation, also in decision-making process, commerce, entrepreneurial Development ,trade and social leadership. Tody very need to enhance Opportunities to women.

Keywords: Digitalisation, Information & Communication Technology, Gender development, Women Empowerment, economic growth.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the shift towards a knowledge society the role of digitalisation in sustainable community and economic development is becoming increasingly important. Many women in rural area are taking leadership in community and economic development activities and are often extremely reliant on a range of communication technologies for personal, family, business and Networking purposes. When we are moving toward 2030 with a greater agenda of Sustainable Development Goals formulated by United Nations, digitalisation has provided many opportunities for women entrepreneurs. In these days digitalisation helps in reducing the gap of gender inequality as it encourage women to take up jobs while fulfilling the responsibilities of house. This is a major contribution towards Goal 5 of Sustainable Development Goals. Many established organisations of the country have their online portals for business whereas many new budding businesses are setting up their exclusively online businesses for its relatively less capital intensive nature. Digitalisation encourages women to grow up their own businesses. E-commerce is well defined by Hunt (2007:1) he provided a complete definition of ecommerce: “e-commerce is the use of electronic communications and digital information processing technology in business transactions to create, transform, and re-define relationships for value creation. In a developing country like India, involvement of women in economic activities is limited by a lack of access to essential resources like education, capital and training etc. In such limited conditions, Digitalisation can be an effective platform for it and contributing to their family income also.

II. OBJECTIVE

This paper focuses on digitalisation and the current ICT tools like e-governance, elearning, e-education, e-finance e-marketing and ICT development like BPO (Business Process Outsourcing) and KPO (Knowledge Process Outsourcing) and their effect on women empowerment in India. We are also looking at the changes there on to the educational system and build up a strong socially viable KNS (Knowledge Network System) and challenges faced by women in such field.

III. SCOPE OF DIGITALISATION AND ICT IN WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Digitalisation comprise a complex and heterogenous set of goods, application and service used to produce, distribute process and transform information. Digitalisation and Communication Technology sector consists of segments as diverse as telecommunications, television and radio broadcasting, computer hardware and software, computer services and electronic media.

IV. IMPACT ON WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

IV.I. LIVELIHOOD

New ICTs provide opportunities to reorganize economic activities in ways that can bypass the traditional dependence of women producers on male-dominated and exploitative market structures, including “middle-men”. In so many times We saw initiatives are being tried that link women artisans directly to global markets through the Internet, as well as support their activities with market and production information. The ‘Inter-city Marketing Network of Women Entrepreneurs’ project in Chennai, India has

set up a communication network among women's community-based organizations (CBOs) to market their produce that impact is that poor women from CBOs constrained by pressures of time and mobility are able to assess and aggregate market demand by trading through their peer CBOs.

IV.II. WORK-LIFE BALANCE

A statement by CEO of the IBM clearly shows the relation between Work Life Balance and gender diversity. He states, "Workplaces support gender diversity and tend to have more flexible work-life balance and family leave policies, that increase women's ability to participate equally in the workforce." — Eric Berridge, CEO of Bluewolf, an IBM Company. Digital technology helps in work life balance of female employees providing inclusive career environment for them. Employees are avoiding work related travels and are organising virtual meetings.

IV.III. COLLABORATION WITH BUSINESS PARTNERS

Digital technology has provided an enormous support to local small and medium scale industries. Working women being tech savvy and helping by small industries of local products like as Indian Handicraft and handloom industry. There is major opportunities of job for women in India through digital technology.

V. CHALLENGES

V.I. GENDER INTERNET USAGE GAP

Women constitute one-third of Internet users in India: According to 'India Inequality Report 2022: Digital Divide' released by the NGO. Indian women are 15 percent less likely to own a mobile phone and 33 percent less likely to use mobile internet services than men.

According to the Mobile Gender Gap Report 2023, compiled by global not-for-profit telecom body GSMA, the gender gap in mobile internet usage in India stood at 40 per cent in 2022, as against 41 percent in 2021

V.II. NEED OF ENHANCEMENT OF E-EDUCATION AND TO BE TECH SAVVY FOR WOMEN

It will be beneficial for women empowerment like as SEWA, Gyandoot, Smile, Disk, Datamation Foundation Etc.

(A) Self Employed Women's Association-(SEWA) uses ICT for women empowerment. The aim of SEWA is to promote local income generating opportunities among women.

(B) GYANDOOT: This project was started in Dhar district of Madhya Pradesh, to fund rural networked cyber kiosks through panchayat.

(C) SMILE: It is Savitri Marketing Institution for Ladies Empowerment is a voluntary organisation in Pune. It project has increased literacy level of women through the usage of Information and communication technology and helped them in marketing they makes various products like as taddy bear,candles, bags, etc.

(D) DATAMATION FOUNDATION: In year 2003 this project started in Seelampur area of Delhi for Muslim women, that localised appropriate communication. Datamation foundation helped link resource-poor women to the information and communication tools for knowledge management.

According to the World Bank data, in 2020, the rural Indian population constitutes 65.05% of the overall population. The total female population in India is 662.90 million. The percentage of Female population is 48.04 percent as compared to 51.96 percent of male population. As per 2011 census, 41.25% of women are illiterates and lack basic educational requirement. Lack of education for women, naturally engages them in very low wage occupations where there is basic need for money.

V.III. INITIAL CAPITAL

Women empowerment through entrepreneurship is not possible if there is unavailability of initial capital. Digitalisation and E-commerce provides an opportunity for women to start their business with little capital with available resources.

VI. CONCLUSION

The Majority of women in India do not have access to digital technology so it is critical if the promise of not leaving anyone behind as per Sustainable development Goals has to be implemented. There are many associations made and policies framed by

various state governments to encourage women to gain maximum through their participation. SEWA (Self Employed Women's Association) in Gujarat, Gyandoot in Madhya Pradesh, Smile in Pune, Datamation Foundation in Delhi There are few of initiatives taken by respective governments to maximise the use of ICT, (Information and communication technology) and digital technology by Women participation. Ecommerce has provided a significant growth for women entrepreneurs and they will contribute to their family income.

VII. SUGGESTION

- Central Government and States Government should be take a good decision for this process of universal access to rights-based information, in rural areas. Digital technology will provide spaces for low price communication .
- Government should adopt legislative to promote gender equality in the digital technology area.
- In India, educational institutes should be conduct such courses that are based on digitalisation and ICT
- Government should be make strong systems to monitor progress towards gender equality in sector of digitalisation.
- Government and society should be promote various schemes for women empowerment through technical expertise and digital technology.

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